

Preparation and Resolution of (\pm)- α -N-Arylamino Acids

N. K. UNDAVIA, M. L. DHANANI and K. A. THAKER

Dept. of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavagar 364002

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(\pm)- α -Phenyl- α -N-arylamino propionic acids have been prepared by acid hydrolysis of (\pm)- α -aminonitriles. The (\pm) acids have been resolved through fractional crystallisation of alkaloidal salts.

\pm - α -AMINOACIDS of proteins have been studied for their physiological activity and have high nutritional value, however, few have been resolved. Tiemann and Priest¹ and Knoevenagel² prepared (\pm) phenyl anilino acetic acid by hydrolysis of (\pm) phenyl anilino acetonitrile, and resolved by McKenzie and Bate³ by fractional crystallisation of (+) cinchonine salt. The resolution of (\pm) α -phenyl- α -N-arylamino propionic acids have not been reported. In search of some new drug potential, the preparation and resolution of (\pm) α -phenyl- α -N-arylamino propionic acids (α - and N substituted alanines) have been undertaken.

(\pm) α -Aminonitriles⁴ prepared from acetophenone, aq. potassium cyanide, glacial acetic acid and aromatic amines were hydrolysed to amides by controlled hydrolysis and amides hydrolysed to acids by dil. sulphuric acid.

(-) Quinine, (+) quinidine, (-) strychnine, and (-) brucine have been tried for the resolution of these (\pm) amine acids (alanines), out of them (-) brucine was found more suitable. (\pm) α -Phenyl- α -anilino, (\pm) α -phenyl- α -(*o*-toluidino) and (\pm) α -phenyl- α -naphthylamino propionic acids have been resolved by fractional crystallisation of their (-) brucine salt.

Experimental

Preparation and optical resolution of (\pm) α -N-arylamino acids

(Compounds prepared were analysed for nitrogen and the nitrogen found agreed with that expected).

(\pm) α -Phenyl- α -N-arylamino nitrile (5 g) was dissolved in cold conc. H_2SO_4 (10 ml) and kept at room temp. for 48 hrs. It was worked up as usual to get (\pm) amide and crystallised from ethanol (95%). (\pm) α -Phenyl-(α -anilino, *o*-toluidino and 1-naphthylamino) propionamides had the m.p. 124°, 119° and 284° respectively.

(\pm) Amide (7 g) was dissolved in conc. H_2SO_4 (55 ml) and water (90 ml) added and refluxed for 6-8 hrs. to get (\pm) acid, crystallised from methanol or methanol pyridine mixed solvent. (\pm) α -Phenyl-(α -anilino, *o*-toluidino and 1-naphthylamino) propionic acids had the m.p. 247°, 241° and 326° respectively

(\pm) Acids obtained were resolved by fractional crystallisation of their 1-brucine salt. α -Phenyl- α -anilino propionic acid has $[\alpha]_D^{20} +93.7^\circ$ and -91.10° (in pyridine) while α -phenyl- α -*o*-toluidino propionic acid and α -phenyl- α -1-naphthylamino propionic acid has $[\alpha]_D^{20} +80.6^\circ$ and -100.7° , and $[\alpha]_D^{20} +156.6^\circ$ and -159.0° respectively.

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